
TO INSTILL IN THE GROWING YOUNGER GENERATION THE CONCEPTS OF HOMELAND, HOMELAND.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7856444>

Mustayev Ruslan Damirovich

Deputy head of the Faculty of Military Education of Fergana State University for educational affairs.

Rahmonberdiyev Muzaffar Ravshanbek o'g'li

cadet of the 19.116th group of the 4th stage of the Faculty of Military Education of Fergana State University

Jamoliddinov Oxunjon Xomidjon o'g'li

cadet of the 19.117th group of the 4th stage of the Faculty of Military Education of Fergana State University

Karimov Abrorjon Alijon o'g'li

cadet of the 19.117th group of the 4th stage of the Faculty of Military Education of Fergana State University

Annotation.

this article describes the upbringing of the growing young generation as highly mature and courageous and instilling in them the concepts of Homeland and patriotism.

Keywords.

Homeland, young generation, Uzbekistan, spirituality, national-value and patriotism of the generation.

Introduction

Love for the motherland will be the cherished dreams of any person in life. A universe of dreams of young people, especially those who are growing up in a free and prosperous homeland, whose hearts are filled with pure emotions. The greatest of these dreams is to serve the parents, elyurt, beminnat, diligently fulfilling the duty of childhood before them. In order to achieve this dream, a person from childhood should set a clear goal for himself, acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and skills, be healthy and energetic, both physically and spiritually.

Result And Discussion

There are many articles aimed at the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism in the media and mass organizations, as well as in schools and higher education institutions.

The national-value and patriotism of the younger generation are common features that are needed to obtain and abide by the rights and freedoms that are of importance to our future country.

The spirit of military patriotism, on the other hand, ensures readiness to serve to preserve the independence of our state. For this reason, special importance should be attached to the upbringing of the younger generation in the spirit of military patriotism.

And to educate the younger generation in the spirit of military patriotism will help them to make decisions for the independence of our country, preserve patriotic ideas of history and play an active role in the development of our country in all areas. The spirit is also important in maintaining individual rights and freedoms.

As the article shows, the spirit of military patriotism should be created in our youth, while special attention should be paid to the understanding of patriotism and national value of the younger generation. This will be of great importance in maintaining important rights and freedoms for the protection of the independence of our state, in obtaining modern knowledge and skills for the profession, in cooperation in social life and in a situation aimed at the development of our country in other areas.

Because great dreams require great aspiration and effort, great energy. On this very difficult and complex path, the feeling of love for the motherland will inspire all of us. Love for the motherland is the greatest feeling. That is why our first president, Islam Karimov, has a special opinion about the role of this feeling in human life, arguing that "the fact of history shows that only a person with national pride, fervor of the motherland will be able to do great deeds. One of the leading, main components of high spirituality is patriotism. Therefore, they approach and interpret the concept of patriotism from different angles. In our opinion, patriotism refers to the fact that a person, appreciating his native land, exerts his strength and enthusiasm for this native land, whatever its sphere. Although not all facets of patriotism are covered in this definition, but the definition is understood correctly if the word appreciation of the motherland itself is approached in a broad sense. To further understand the concept of patriotism, it is necessary to perfectly study the works of Furqat, Fitrat, Abdullah Qadiri, Chulpan, Abdullah Avlani, Uthman Nasir, Hamid Olimjan, Ghafur Ghulam, Erkin Vohidov, Abdullah Oripov. Patriotism should be absorbed in the blood and blood of a person. In this place, our first president was I.A.Karimov said: "love for the land, for the Motherland, for

Humanistic feelings is a long-standing feature that is embedded in the blood and blood of our people. The question of preserving and further improving these unique long-standing qualities and raising our children as worthy sons and daughters of a free and Democratic Uzbekistan should form the main direction of our work in the field of spirituality." Only when each person has his own homeland can he become a true patriot. Discussion and conclusion

Patriotism is to cultivate the land, land, elinie, where she was born and raised, to care for her economic, social, political, cultural, spiritual progress, to care for, to make her worthy contribution to progress, to strive to preserve the independence of her state, her country, and, if necessary, to devote her life to it. A sense of patriotism is glorified not only in secular instruction, but also in our religion. The most invaluable among what a person has is his religion and Homeland. There is no man who does not glorify his homeland. For the Fatherland is the land where the blood of his navel is shed, where the child passed, took his first steps, pushed through youth, old age, his memories were sealed, the land of his ancestors, where his children and grandchildren grew up! See the dwarf Ant, how many places it goes on the demand for sustenance, difficulty climbing the hills. This also returns to his ini - Homeland. Some animals die if they are moved from their original homeland to another place. You see, everyone loves their homeland, from a human being to small insects. So it is the custom of God in these creatures, the law that he has issued! He was put into the human Fitrat by God. What makes them live in warm places, where the temperature reaches sixty, or in the north poles, where the temperature is below zero, or in forests, in life-threatening lands every day?! What motivates them to do is just love for their homeland. A person has several fees and duties before his homeland. The most important of them are three: to truly fall in love with their homeland; to beautify their homeland. This is how God blesses him:" he has made you appear from the Earth, and he has placed you in it for his prosperity " (HUD, 61). Not to be obsessed with the affairs of corruption and corruption in the motherland. This is how the Qur'an is blessed in Karim: "and do not make corruption in the Earth after it is reformed (A'raf,56). Sheikh Muhammad Ghazzali (rahmatullahi alayh) of the hamasr scholars said a very beautiful description of the Homeland, writing in small and neat, gilded letters: "humanity loved its land with its things, even if it was a desert where no one lived. The place where love is embedded in the heart, where a person is calm when he is in it, where he is talpin ' when he is far away, where he protects when he is attacked, where he is angry when he is humiliated is the Homeland". The task of teachers is to pass on

Love and respect for the motherland to the younger generations, for its historical past. It is necessary to help children become worthy citizens of their country and strive to preserve and develop its traditions and cultural values. In the educational system, patriotic education of students is very important. Experts believe that children perceive the first visions of society, tevarak-environment, existence at the age of 3 to 7 years. The main thing is that it is these information that will remain in memory for the rest of your life.

Conclusion: therefore, to educate our youth in the spirit of patriotism, it pays to start education and upbringing from preschool educational institutions. The development of patriotism is the main task of any country. A patriot is a person for whom the fate of the state has always been the first. But this attitude arises only from a reliable person: his country protects in a difficult time, helps the family. Therefore, we should not be forced to become a patriot of the survivors of poverty, people should have something to be proud of, and especially their well-being, their backs, achievements should be protected.